

STRATEGIES OF MANAGERIAL ACTIVITY IN DIRECTING HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS TO THE PROFESSION

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Abstract. *The content of vocational orientation of students State educational standards, curriculum, program, textbooks, specific aspects of a specific topic and type of training, existing pedagogical conditions, age and psychological characteristics of students, their vital needs and interests, the level of knowledge and skills of the teacher and other factors are determined. Step-by-step explanation of managerial activity strategies, elements of successful strategic management, etc. in guiding students of general education schools to the profession ensures the effectiveness of this activity. The article says that in order to monitor the changes in the business environment, in order to create its own strategy, students should be taught to study the needs of the organization, take into account the set of necessary rules, actions and decisions.*

Keywords: *strategy, process, direction, development, organization, opportunity, value, market, business, innovation, material, success.*

Introduction

Vocational training is aimed at helping students to make the right choice of profession and to acquire a profession that matches their personal qualities.

In the course of education, students should be able to independently study the world of professions, be able to compare the requirements of the chosen profession with their own personal qualities, and correctly assess their inclination, ability, health, suitability for the chosen profession. All this will help each student to choose the right profession, determine the most optimal way to acquire it.

The content of guiding students to the profession is the state education standards, curriculum, program, as well as specific aspects of a specific topic and type of training in textbooks, manuals, existing pedagogical conditions, the age and psychological characteristics of students, their vital needs and interests, the teacher's knowledge and it is determined based on the level of competence, worldview, creativity, assessment of the situation and the ability to act quickly in accordance with it, and other factors. Its diagnostically clear and clear reflection makes it possible to draw a conclusion about the level of organization and implementation of the didactic process when it is known and implemented.

Issues of guiding students to profession Mavlonova R., Nishonaliev U.N., Tolipov O'.Q., Khodjaboev A.R., Shodiev N.Sh. and other pedagogic scientists and explained in their textbooks, methodological manuals and recommendations.

As the foreign scientist G. Romantsev noted, a new type of personality is being formed, which, according to its characteristics, is fundamentally different from the type of personality raised in the conditions of the administrative-command system of management and planned production [13]. "Inculcation of knowledge, skills and competences of future professional activity in a specialist" no longer ensures his professional competence due to rapid changes in the content

of work and updating of practical knowledge, because the obsolescence rate of the profession in industrialized countries is about 8 years, and in some sectors 5 years, that is, every specialist 20-30% of knowledge is "undervalued" every year [8].

The need to constantly update knowledge is put forward as a basic principle. This means the need to significantly activate the educational process, as well as to develop a professional personality capable of continuous self-improvement and self-development during the educational process, which ensures the development of professionally important personal qualities that guarantee the formation of professional competence and competitiveness of a person [14]. The above is fully applicable to the modern education system, which is currently undergoing only organizational changes, which do not affect the goal adjustments that lead to a change in the nature of the educational process.

Understanding and uncovering the basis of the choice of profession cannot be understood without applying the objective reasons to life. One of these reasons is the division of labor. Research scientist K. Davlatov has published a number of works on career orientation of students [4]. The main topic of these works was to study the opinions of students. He stated that material and spiritual division of work is necessary in human activity. In today's society, the division of labor reflects the nature of market relations. Mental work belongs to talented professions, and physical labor belongs to mass professions.

Although the division of labor is preserved in the system of market relations, it acquires a different nature. Even so, relations in production, taking advantage of the social advantage of the new society, the high mechanization of work, automation and the use of computers will increase the efficiency of work. Adaptation of machines and other equipment to people, proper organization of work and rest, improvement of cultural and technical conditions of workers and specialists, improvement of skills of all workers-specialists is an urgent task.

The market economy imposes special requirements on the specialist to participate in the development of production, to ensure the high quality of products with rapidly changing and technologically complex characteristics, to limit the increase in the cost of products by improving production methods and reducing costs. In addition, "requirements for the quality of educational services in the development of the non-state sector of the economy are already being strengthened. Rigorous competitive selection in recruitment dramatically increases the criteria and parameters of the quality of professional training..." [13]. Employers are interested in creating competitiveness and increasing their intangible assets, as well as quality vocational training. Vocational education system that prepares future specialists for various sectors of the economy should take into account their needs. E.F. Zeer said, "...so now there is a need to fundamentally restructure the entire process of vocational education. It is important for a potential specialist to prepare for work in the market economy and competitive conditions" [5].

Today, it is necessary to choose the right profession, take into account the demands placed on specialists in the division of labor, determining the balance between mental and physical work. As you know, various requirements are imposed on specialists, the first of which is high-quality training, and the second is special mental qualities and a high level of skill. Therefore, even healthy people cannot get the profession they want because of their mental state. For example: the driver should be resistant to sudden mental influences, not lose his temper in the event of an accident. There are some people who know the causes of an accident on paper and know how to eliminate it, but in the event of an accident, they are completely unable to control themselves.

The main task of general education schools is to ensure all-round development of students, to restore their aesthetic and physical education, to restore their health, to teach them to work, to direct them to choose a specific profession, to prepare students for life.

Method

It is not possible to deviate from the ability in the career orientation of students of general education schools. A labor activity chosen by a person does not leave him throughout his life, this labor activity remains an integral part of a person's place in society. A person expresses his attitude to the world through his profession, and it is precisely through this profession that he finds his place in society. A correctly chosen profession plays a key role in the development of a person into a well-rounded person and in hormonal development.

It is necessary to explain the word strategy before determining the requirements for the strategies of managerial activity in the career orientation of students of general education schools. Strategy means the art of generalship in Greek. Strategy for an organization refers to a set of rules, actions, and decisions that guide the organization's activities in order to achieve goals, transform organizational needs into resources for change.

The strategy process does not end with any quick action. It usually ends with the establishment of general directions, the development of which ensures the improvement and strengthening of the position of the organization.

Benchmark represents the goal that the organization wants to achieve, and strategy represents the means to achieve the goal. A reference point is a high level of decision making. In other words, there are different ways to achieve the goal. For example, the organization set a goal: by the end of the three-year period, it is necessary to ensure a 50% increase in turnover and a 60% increase in profit. There are different ways to achieve this goal:

- increasing the market share due to already manufactured products;
- expanding the market by increasing the types of manufactured products;
- access to new, possibly international markets;
- reduction of production costs;
- expansion of production capacity through vertical integration without changing the sales volume of the final product;
- growth through acquisition or merger, etc.

Three information blocks are used as a basis for building the organization's strategy:

- forecasts of the economic situation;
- analysis of the organization's capabilities;
- organizational strategy.

Forecasting the economic situation is usually considered in three aspects:

- analysis of future threats and opportunities;
- elimination of unexpected events;
- search for new competitive technologies in business [9].

One of the vital prerequisites for strategy is the occurrence of drastic changes in the external environment of the organization. They may be due to demand saturation, major changes in technology inside or outside the organization, or the unexpected appearance of major competitors.

When faced with such a situation, the organization faces two very difficult problems:

- choosing the desired growth direction from among many alternatives;
- directing the efforts of a large team in the right direction.

In fact, the answer to these questions is found in the essence of development and the implementation of strategies. At such times, strategy becomes a vital and necessary management tool. Examples of possible strategies include:

- An attack strategy with high risk and high payoff potential. The implementation of scientific and technical innovations requires certain skills and the ability to see new market prospects.

- Defense strategy. Suitable for organizations that generate revenue in a competitive environment and are strong in marketing and production.

- Licensing - often used by firms with an aggressive strategy.

- Intermediate strategy. It is based on conscious avoidance of direct confrontation with competitors and identification of their weaknesses.

- Advanced technology. Creating a new market that allows you to launch a completely new product.

It can be seen that the need for a new organizational strategy can be updated with changes in the demands of society.

Results and discussion

The strategy formation process can be represented by a chain: the purpose of the organization - its goals - assessment and analysis of the external environment - analysis of the organization's resources - development of strategic alternatives - analysis and selection of the strategy - implementation of the strategy. - evaluation of implementation - correction of strategy. It is necessary to explain the algorithm of creating a management strategy of one's own organization, taking into account the strategies of managerial activities in the career guidance of students of general education schools.

There is no universal algorithm of strategic planning: each organization has its own decisions and the sequence of their implementation. The most objective and effective model of creating one's own management strategy can be shown as follows:

Analysis of business profitability. The dynamics of recent years analyze the overall profitability of the organization and its individual branches. Based on the results, the next action of the organization is planned.

Analysis of the market situation. It is necessary to determine the position of the organization in relation to competitors. Job analysis allows you to evaluate the organization for its merits.

Analysis of competitors' activities, evaluation of their further actions. This point comes from the past: after assessing the situation, its forecast is made. When developing a strategy, it is important to consider the actions of competitors as an external factor.

Analysis of the current activity of the organization. At this stage of strategic planning, the external and internal environment factors of the organization are determined. Based on the obtained data, it is possible to draw a conclusion about which business sectors are lagging behind the market average and which are superior.

Analysis of development opportunities. According to the results of the last stage, the most promising directions of business can be determined. Real opportunities for growth are based on performance that is inferior to competitors or not at all.

Assessment of further development. At this stage, the organization's potential for further competition in the market is determined. The development of the organization depends on financing and distribution of funds, so it is important to determine their sources and directions.

Choosing a strategy. After all the remaining stages, a choice can be made in favor of specific strategies.

Summary

Managerial activity strategies in career orientation of secondary school students is a complex and multifaceted process that includes many aspects. It is the creation and implementation of a business strategy based on an analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats, as well as an understanding of market trends and consumer values.

Successful management requires constant study and analysis of the market, business processes and competitive offers. This includes researching news, materials and research in the areas where the organization operates.

Teaching management strategies to students of general education schools begins with explaining the main elements of business strategy, cost and income management, and successful strategic management. It is important to constantly monitor changes in the business environment and create and adapt one's strategy to achieve goals and ensure future success.

REFERENCES

1. Боймуродова Ч.Ў. “Педагогикамизда халқ меҳнатининг шакли, усули ва мазмуни”. Андижон машинасозлик институти илмий-оммабоб журнали. Андижон шаҳри. 2-сон. 2021 й.
2. Боймуродова Ч.Ў. “Шахсни камолга етказиш ва ҳаётга тайёрлашда меҳнат тарбиясининг аҳамияти”. “Педагогик таълим кластери: муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусида халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман материаллари. Чирчиқ шаҳри. 25- 26 июнь 2021 йил. 516-518 бетлар.
3. Гаппаров Б.Н. ва бошқалар. “Халқ педагогикаси”. “Тафаккур” нашриёти. - Т: 2009. 211-214 бетлар.
4. Давлатов К., Воробьев А., Каримов И. Меҳнат ва касб таълими назарияси ҳамда методикаси. - Тошкент., Ўқитувчи, 1992. - 320 б.
Мильнер Б.З. «Теория организации: Учебник», 3-е изд., М.: ИНФРА-М, 2003. – с.154-155.
5. Зеер, Э. Ф. Психология профессии / Э.Ф Зеер. - М.: Академический Проект, 2003. 336 с.
6. Иноятов У.И., Муслимов Н.А., ва бошқ. Педагогика: 1000 та саволга 1000 та жавоб. 2012 й. Тошкент, “Илм-Зиё” нашриёти. 12 б.т.
7. Муслимов Н., ва бошқалар. Касб таълими ўқитувчиларининг касбий компетентлигини шакллантириш технологияси. – Т.: “Фан ва технологиялар”, 2013 й. 8 б.т.
8. Никитина, Н.Н. Основы профессионально-педагогической деятельности / Н.Н. Никитина, О.М. Железнякова, М.А. Петухов. - М.: Мастерство, 2002. - 288 с.
9. «Основы менеджмента»: Учеб.пособие / Н. И. Кабушкин.-6-е изд., стереотип.- Мн.:Новое знание, 2003.-168-169 с.
10. Педагогика назарияси ва тарихи // М.Х. Тўхтаўжаева таҳрири остида. –Т.: “Молия-иктисод”, 2008.-208 б.

11. Подласый И. Педагогика. Новый курс: учебник для студ. педаг. вузов. - в 2-х кн. – М.: ВЛАДОС, 1999.-567 с.
12. Раззоқов Б.Х. Миллий кадриятлар воситасида бўлажак ўқитувчиларнинг касб маданиятини шакллантириш. Муғаллим хам узликсиз билимлендириу. Нукус-2021. № 3/3. 52-54 б.
13. Романцев, Г.М. Теоретические основы высшего профессионального образования / Г.М. Романцев. - Екатеринбург : Уральский государственный профессионально-педагогический университет. - 1997. - 332 с.
14. Спирин, Л.Ф. Теория и технология решения педагогических задач (развивающееся профессионально-педагогическое обучение и самообразование) / Л.Ф. Спирин; под ред. П.И. Пидкасистого. - М. : Изд-во «Российское педагогическое агентство», 1997. - 174 с.
15. Шарипов Ш.С., Воробьев А.И., Муслимов Н.А., Исмоилова М. Касб таълими педагогикаси. - Тошкент., 2005. - 58 б.
16. Юнусов М.Р. Махсус мактабларда хунармандчиликка босқичма-босқич ўқитишнинг илмий - методик асослари. Пед. Фан. Ном. Дисс., автореферат, 1998 й.
17. “Ўзбек педагогикаси тарихи”, проф. А.Зуннунов таҳрири остида, Тошкент.1997 йил, 27-бет.
18. Ўрта Осиёда педагогик фикр тараққиётдан лавҳалар. Тошкент – 1996 йил, 180-бет.